

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: N'dri****FIRST NAME: Kouadio Jean****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Introduction (EUCLID 2021, 1-13)
2. Communication resources (EUCLID 2022)
3. Course content (PHGH 2022, 5)
4. Zotero (EUCLD 2021, 2)
5. Writing framework (EUCLID 2021, 7)
6. Conclusion
7. References

ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I went through the first period of this ACA-401D program. The indications are relevant, and the videos posted in high definition are helpful for course understanding. The orientations are indicated with precision, and the various resources I could access gave me an overview of the importance of an academic document. This is all the more so since this course, as part of obtaining a doctorate, is devoted to a teaching purpose. I admit that this first experience reinforces my choice of university and the online asynchronous learning mode promoted by EUCLID.

As a humanitarian worker, I was looking for a flexible program to fit the various constraints of my schedule (EUCLID 2021, 13). While skimming through, I could see a low-tuition program where applicants can start at any time. EUCLID is also a flexible program where students can ask for deadlines extension. Furthermore, I was struck by the information I could access on the website to indicate the work that awaited me. Through the advertising page, I could get answers to the questions I was asking myself. In addition,

a legitimacy section devoted to alums and peers is available at any time. I could also access the accreditation making the university a unique intergovernmental higher learning institution (EUCLID 2021, 1). The content of this first course showed me the importance of an academic paper. It deals with a writing framework focused on rules depending on the type of academic document, which can be a response or a significant piece. Anyway, Zotero is recommended in parenthetical citation editing. Some recommendations on TURABIAN's author-date style (EUCLID 2021, 6) and some plagiarism and third-party citing rules have to be followed.

In this response paper, I will start by commenting on the communication resources that lead a first-time visitor to the website. Then regarding the course, I will comment on the content, cast an overview on Zotero, and finally, the writing framework

2) COMMUNICATION RESOURCES

The general organization of the website presents precise and easily accessible indications, even for a first-time visitor. The division between the course management system focused on administration, finances, and course progression, and the learning management system concentrated on the central part of the course illustrates the communication fluidity. On the course management system side, I was comforted by reading the list of EUCLID's international organizations partners in the left column of my screen. In the central part of the screen, I could see various tables dealing with programs, student progressive learning, etc. The learning management system page has the same layout as the course management system site. On the left side of the screen, I could find the course periods ranging from one to seven (EUCLID 2022).

Then some high-resolution videos of about a quarter an hour allow the complete information to be passed on without losing the thread to the learner. The first one, introducing the Grammarly application, is a seven-minute video on how to make academic writing bold and clear. The video shows a tutorial on downloading, installing, and using Grammarly. Then a lecturing video of 12 minutes on Zotero installation is advertised. The instructors adopted an easy-to-understand communication technique for all audiences in these videos.

Communication with the office for admission and the course instructor is also impeccable. I could get quick feedback emails from the questions I sent them.

3) COURSE CONTENT

The course content is disclosed through Standard textbooks, DVD lecture/online videos, MP3 podcasts and Webcast, internal EUCLID course packs, and moderate conference calls (PHGH 2022, 5).

For the first course, ACA-401D period 1, only a student orientation PDF and some password-protected YouTube videos are available. Students can contact the course

instructor for further explanation at any time. The student orientation document is the study material that contains some illustrations, rules, and recommendations on writing an excellent academic paper.

4) ZOTERO

Zotero, used in referencing management, facilitates the tedious task of manual bibliographic collection. A beginner's guide is advertised in a twelve-minutes video. This video shows how to install Zotero software and organize one's library. The chosen rule style for referencing is TURABIAN or WHO for global health students (EUCLID 2021, 2). A screenshot presenting an organized Zotero table is visible on the learning management system's page.

5) WRITING FRAMEWORK

The first rule that frames the academic writing style for producing a response paper is the number of pages. It comprises between 3 and 5 pages written on the most recent EUCLID template. This template specifies indications on interline spacing and the use of parenthesis. According to this document, the plagiarism rate must be checked through the Grammarly application. While inserting a citation, one cannot just copy-paste a text or a sample of text even though adding a footnote.

A standard response paper has the shape of seven headings written on a Microsoft word specific template. This template contains the title details, the classic style for the body of text, a quote, and a heading style. While writing, some everyday things could be improved, like adding blank spaces and using contractive forms to avoid (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Academic writing respects punctuation rules. For example, a period can only appear in a sentence with a verb or never put two periods in one sentence. To comply with academic writing, American and British English can be used. However, the one selected should be specified on the form, and some rules of period and parenthesis in/out need to be respected.

6) CONCLUSION

EUCLID's distance teaching shows considerable advantages for a part-time student.

Writing a bold and clear academic document involves following a specific frame. A set of rules in PDF and videos to write a strong paper are available online.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

EUCLID. Course period page. ACA-401 period1 <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.